

**ELUCIDATING THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND
ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF A THERAPEUTICALLY IMPORTANT
AND ENDANGERED ORCHID, *AERIDES MULTIFLORA* ROXB. FROM
NORTHWESTERN HIMALAYAS**

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation was carried out with an objective to determine the total phenolics and flavonoids, and antioxidant activity and further the characterization of the bioactive phytochemical constituents in a therapeutically important orchid, *Aerides multiflora* using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) technique. Ethanolic leaf extract was found to contain the highest total phenolics and the highest total flavonoids with a value of 88.92 ± 0.014 mg gallic acid equivalent per g dry weight and 101.13 ± 0.02 mg rutin equivalent per g dry weight, respectively. The antioxidant activity of leaf and root was evaluated by DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) free radical scavenging assay. The major compounds identified from GC-MS analysis were Octadecanoic acid, Lidocaine, n-Hexadecanoic acid, 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid(Z,Z)-, Tetrapentacontane, Stigmasterol *etc.* The present study aimed to investigate the phytochemical profile of

this orchid; identify a range of bioactive compounds through GC-MS analysis; pharmacological activities of these compounds demonstrating its potential as a source for novel drug development.

KEYWORDS: Phytochemical, Flavonoid, Phenol, Alkaloids, Therapeutic, Secondary metabolites.

INTRODUCTION

Orchids have tremendous therapeutic potential due to presence of selective phytochemicals like alkaloids, bibenzyl compounds, flavonoids, phenanthrenes *etc.* in abundant quantity with excellent antibacterial, anticancer, anti-inflammatory and antiviral properties.^[1,2] The different compounds that have been isolated earlier from orchids [Moscatin (*Dendrobium loddigesii*),^[3] Dendroside A (*Dendrobium nobile*),^[4] Dendrobine (*Dendrobium nobile*),^[5] Chrysin (*Cypripedium macranthos*),^[6] Cremastrine (*Cremastra appendiculata*)^[7] *etc.*] have demonstrated significant activities against various diseases Orchids exhibiting the therapeutic and pharmaceutical compounds, ultimately guide lead discovery toward new drugs.^[8] Active traditional medicines from orchids, which have been used to treat various diseases have been known for the past centuries, hence there is an urgent need to document and screen them.

Aerides multiflora Roxb. commonly known as *Draupadi Puspa* belongs to the genus *Aerides* Lour. of the “foxtail orchids” from family Orchidaceae, especially known for its attractive flowers and foliage. The plant is indigenous to India, Bangladesh, Nepal, Myanmar, Thailand, Malaysia, Philippines, Laos, Cambodia, and Vietnam. In India, it is geographically distributed over North-Western Himalayas, Sikkim, West Bengal, and Arunachal Pradesh. It can grow at a wide range of altitudinal elevations from 150-1200 m amsl from low and tropical to subtropical forests. The species is commonly used for treating wounds, bacterial infections, and is known to possess antidiabetic property;^[9,10] the species is also used in conventional breeding programs for the development of new hybrids.^[11]

Screening of medicinal plants by various chromatographic and spectrometric methods provides information on their chemical and pharmacological activity, which aids in the selection of biologically active plants. These methods are useful for the proper standardization of herbal drug formulations.^[12,13] In recent years, GC-MS analysis and quantification techniques are widely used for isolation and identification of bioactive molecules^[14,15,16] in a few orchid species. However, there is very less information available on the detailed analysis of bioactive constituents present in this plant. Hence, this study was planned to conduct a comprehensive examination to determine the total phenolic and flavonoid content, identify new bioactive compounds and assess their antioxidant capacity which may provide an insight into its use in traditional medicine.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection of plant material

The plant material was collected from Sarkaghat District Mandi, Himachal Pradesh (India) in the month of June, 2023. Fresh, disease-free plant parts (Leaf and root) were thoroughly washed with tap water followed by washing with distilled water and then dried in the shade at room temperature ($25\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) until they became well dried; these were ground into fine powder by using grinder and placed into a well closed container and subsequently labelled and stored till further use.

Plant extract preparation

Plant parts (leaf and root) powder (2 g) mixed with aqueous and ethanol solvents (30 ml), in conical flasks was kept on an orbital shaker at room temperature for 48 hours. The mixture was then filtered through muslin cloth and resultant filtrate was again filtered through Whatman's Filter No.1. The final extracts were collected in falcon tubes and stored in refrigerator (4°C) till further use.

Quantitative phytochemical screening

Determination of total phenolic content (TPC) by Folin-Ciocalteu assay

Total phenol content in the leaf and root extracts was determined by using Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent (FCR).^[17] In the procedure, different concentrations of the extracts were mixed with 0.5 mL FCR (diluted 1:10 v/v). After 5 minutes, 1.5 mL of 20% sodium carbonate solution (Na_2CO_3) was added. The final volume of the tubes was made up to 10 mL with distilled water. The FCR reagent oxidizes phenols in plant extracts and changes into the dark blue colour which was then shaken well and incubated for 2 hours at room temperature. Then, the absorbance was measured at 750 nm against blank by UV-visible spectrophotometer. The samples were prepared in triplicates for each analysis, and the average value of absorbance obtained at different concentrations of gallic acid was used to plot the calibration curve to determine the level of phenolics in the extracts. The same procedure was repeated for standard gallic acid solution and standard curve obtained. Total phenolic content of the extracts was expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram of sample in dry weight (mgg^{-1}). The following formula was used to determine the total phenolic content of the extract with gallic acid equivalent.^[18]

$$\text{TPC} = C \times V/M$$

Where TPC is the Total Phenolic Content

‘C’ is the concentration of phenolic calculated from the equation obtained from the calibration curve

‘V’ is the volume of the extracts added for the test (mL)

‘M’ is the weight of extracts

Determination of total flavonoid content (TFC) by Aluminium chloride method

The total flavonoid content of leaf and root extracts was determined with slight modification in the method of Saeed *et al.*^[19] Different concentrations of the extracts were mixed with 5% NaNO₂ solution (0.3 mL), and after 5 minutes of incubation, 10% AlCl₃ solution (0.3 mL) was added, and then solution was allowed to stand for 6 minutes. Then, 1M NaOH solution (2 mL) was added, and the final volume of the mixture was brought to 10 mL with distilled water. The mixture was mixed thoroughly, and absorbance was taken at 510 nm. The same procedure was repeated for standard rutin solution and standard curve obtained. The total flavonoid content was calculated from a calibration curve, and the result was expressed as mg rutin equivalent per gram of sample in dry weight (mgg⁻¹). The following formula was used to determine the total flavonoid content in the extract with rutin equivalent.^[18]

$$\text{TFC} = C \times V / M$$

Where TFC is the Total Flavonoid Content

‘C’ is the concentration of flavonoid calculated from the equation obtained from the calibration curve

‘V’ is the volume of the extracts added for the test (mL)

‘M’ is the weight of extracts

Antioxidant activity

Preparation of plant extracts for antioxidant evaluation

Plant parts (leaf and root) powder (1 g) were soaked in 25 mL of methanol (99%) samples were put in a shaking water bath at 100 rounds per minute (rpm) for 2.5 hr at room temperature. After 2.5 hr, the samples were centrifuged for 15 minutes at 6000-8000 rpm. The supernatant was then filtered using filter papers, collected and further used for the antioxidant testing.

DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity

The free radical scavenging activity was measured by using DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) with little modification in the method of McCune and Johns.^[20] Different concentrations (15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 60, and 80 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) of samples prepared were added to freshly prepared 1M DPPH (1 mL) methanol solution and mixed. Reaction mixture was incubated in dark at room temperature for 25-30 minutes. The same procedure was repeated for standard ascorbic acid solution and standard curve obtained. Decrease in the absorbance of the tested samples was monitored at 517 nm using a UV spectrophotometer. Methanol serves as blank. The sample concentration providing 50% inhibition (IC_{50}) was calculated by plotting the inhibition percentages against the concentrations of the sample. All tests were carried out in triplicate and IC_{50} values were reported as means. Inhibition of free radical DPPH in per cent (%) was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = [1 - (A/B)] \times 100$$

Where, 'A' Absorbance of sample; 'B' Absorbance of control

Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) Analysis

Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of the extracts was performed using a GC-MS (GCMS-TQ8050 NX). The sample was injected into the injected port of the Gas chromatography (GC) device. The injection port temperature was maintained at 250°C and the column oven temperature was initially set at 70°C for 5 minutes, which was subsequently ramped to 310°C at rate of 5°C /minute and held for 10 minutes. The *Aerides multiflora* leaf and root extract (1 mg) dissolved in required volume of ethanol was injected into GC and the chromatogram was obtained in the time range of 63 min. The relative percentage constituents of the each extract was expressed as percentage with peak area. The peak in GC-MS spectrum represents the presence of the secondary phytochemical compounds. The identification of components was based on reference standard data of National Institute Standard and Technology (NIST) library. The constituents were identified after comparison with those available in the computer library attached to the GC-MS instrument and the results obtained, have been tabulated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quantitative phytochemical screening

Phenol and flavonoid compounds are commonly found in medicinal plants, vegetables, and fruits; these have been reported to have multiple biological activities.^[21] Phenolics,

flavonoids, tannins, and alkaloids represent major groups of plant constituents which predominantly work as powerful antioxidants or scavenger of free radicals. These are beneficial for human health and serve as important remedies for various inflammatory disorders, cancer, and diabetes which mainly occur due to the deregulation of free radical generation in the cells.^[22] Orchids are known to have various secondary metabolites, but only a few of them have been so far evaluated. Primarily Orchids are known to contain phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, carotenoids, and sterols. Presence of polyphenols has also been reported in *Habenaria edgeworthii* by Giri et al.^[23]

As *A. multiflora*, is one of the most important therapeutic and endangered orchid of NorthWestern Himalayas, the knowledge of the biochemical constitution of its various parts is essential. During the present study variations were observed in the total phenolic and flavonoid contents of its different parts *i.e.* root and leaf (Table 1). Presently, ethanolic leaf extract of the plant exhibited the highest phenolic content (88.92 ± 0.014 mgGAE/gDW) whereas, aqueous root extract showed the lowest phenolic content (35.46 ± 0.002 mgGAE/gDW) (Fig. 1A). According to Beyhan et al.^[24], phenolic compounds are associated with antioxidant activity and play a significant role in stabilizing lipid peroxidation. Flavonoids quench down the free radicals by reducing their levels significantly and thereby upregulating or protecting antioxidant defense. In the present study, the highest concentration of flavonoids was found in the ethanolic leaf extract (101.13 ± 0.02 mgQE/gDW) whereas the least was found in the aqueous leaf extract of the plant (62.86 ± 0.01 mgQE/gDW) (Fig. 1B). Our findings revealed that the contents of phenolic and flavonoid components are vary with the solvent system used as well as with the plant part used. Similar variations in phenolic and flavonoid contents (with in the plant parts) were reported earlier in various medicinal plants such as *Anacamptis morio* (Orchidaceae^[25]), *A. pyramidalis* (Orchidaceae^[25]), *Calotropis gigantea* (Asclepiadaceae^[26]), *Calanthe tricarinata* (Orchidaceae^[27]), *Decalepis hamiltoni* (Periplocaceae^[26]), *Dendrobium nobile* (Orchidaceae^[28]), *Dendrobium sp.* Sonia, Sonia Pink, Snow Rabbit and Shavin White (Orchidaceae^[29]), *Hemidesmus indicus* (Apocynaceae^[26]), *Neotinea tridentate* (Orchidaceae^[26]), *Ophrys mammosa* (Orchidaceae^[26]), *O. lutea* (Orchidaceae^[26]), *Rhynchostylis retusa* (Orchidaceae^[27]), *Vanda cristata* (Orchidaceae^[30]). Such variations might be due to the hormonal content, and specific metabolic as well as endogenous physiological changes taking place in the plants. Similar conclusions were earlier arrived at by Bhattacharyya et al.^[28]

Table 1: Total Phenol and Flavonoids contents using two solvents in *A. multiflora* Leaf and Root parts.

Plant part used	TPC (mg gallic acid equivalent /g dry weight)		TFC (mg rutin equivalent /g dry weight)	
	Aqueous	Ethanol	Aqueous	Ethanol
Leaf	40.49±0.015	88.92±0.014	62.86±0.01	101.13±0.02
Root	35.46±0.002	68.74±0.042	73.73±0.016	96.93±0.01

Data represents the mean ±Standard error (SE).

A

B

Fig. 1A-B. A, Histogram representing TPC in aqueous and ethanol extract of *A. multiflora* leaf and root; B, Histogram representing TFC in aqueous and ethanol extract of *A. multiflora* leaf and root parts.

Antioxidant activity

The antioxidant potential of the methanolic extract of *A. multiflora* leaf and root was observed using DPPH and Ascorbic acid as a reference standard to identify the DPPH radical scavenging activity. In the DPPH assay, the antioxidants react with the stable free radical *i.e.*, 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (deep purple colour) and convert it to 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazine with discolouration. The degree of discolouration indicates the scavenging potentials of the sample antioxidant. A standard curve was made and DPPH activity was observed by measuring OD at 517 nm. It was observed that per cent inhibition ranges between 11.356%-98.342% (leaf extract) and 17.446%-92.733% (root extract) at different extract concentrations *i.e.* 15-80 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (Fig.2). IC_{50} values of leaf and root extracts were found 21.219 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 35.839 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ respectively (Table 2). It was earlier suggested by many researchers that bioactive compounds such as ascorbic acid, tocopherol, flavonoids, polyphenols, tannins *etc.* reduce and decolourize DPPH via their hydrogen-donating ability.^[26,30,31] According to Mukherjee *et al.*,^[32] *Dendrobium aqueum* extract showed a dose dependent DPPH free-radical scavenging potential and exhibited a significant antiglycation potential. Hoque *et al.*^[33] worked on the antioxidant potential of an epiphytic orchid, *Eria lasiopetala* and the highest mean scavenging activity of leaf and stem was observed as 82.07% and 82.27%, respectively at 250 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ concentration. *Dendrobium moniliforme* was also reported to have potential antioxidant activity and it showed the highest percentage of DPPH radical scavenging activity (94.48%).^[34] Pathak *et al.*^[30] reported as 143.06 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 54.13 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in *Vanda cristata* leaf and root extracts IC_{50} values respectively.

Table 2: Percentage of 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radicals scavenged by *A. multiflora* leaf and root extracts at different concentrations.

Concentration of extract ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Leaf extract (per cent inhibition)	Root extract (per cent inhibition)
15	11.356 \pm 1.87	17.446 \pm 1.75
20	47.074 \pm 1.12	18.907 \pm 1.06
25	58.417 \pm 0.35	39.425 \pm 1.28
30	83.172 \pm 0.88	49.011 \pm 1.08
40	87.397 \pm 0.26	69.047 \pm 0.65
60	94.343 \pm 0.11	86.83 \pm 0.27
80	98.342 \pm 0.04	92.733 \pm 0.15
IC_{50} Value	21.219 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$	35.839 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$

Fig. 2: Plot showing the DPPH radical scavenging percentage activity of *A. multiflora* leaf and root extracts.

GC-MS Analysis

The analysis and extraction of plant material play an important role in the development, modernization and quality control of herbal formulations. During the present study, GC-MS analysis of different plant parts in *Aerides multiflora* has revealed the presence of various phytochemicals, thereby pointing toward its prospective usage in pharmaceutical industries. The total number of compounds detected in different parts vary and have been shown in Fig. 4(A-B). The compounds found in root and leaf (aqueous and ethanol) extract along with their retention time (RT), area (%), Compound, CAS, molecular weight, molecular formula, and chemical structure are presented in the Tables 3, 4, 5 and 6.

Analysis of ethanol extract of *A. multiflora* roots revealed the presence of 28 phytoactive compounds. Comparable to this, aqueous extract of *A. multiflora* roots showed 20 compounds. Of these 13 compounds were common between the two different solvent extract of root (Fig. 4 A). Amongst the detected compounds, the concentrations of Octadecanoic acid, Lidocaine, n-Hexadecanoic acid, 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, Tetrapentacontane, Stigmasterol were more in the ethanol extract of root observed from the percentages of their peak areas in the chromatograms (Fig. 3A). Likewise in aqueous root extract maximum concentration was of Cyclodecasiloxane, eicosamethyl- followed by Cyclooctasiloxane, hexadecamethyl-, Benzene, 1,3-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-, Behenic alcohol, and Dotriacontane, in decreasing order of their % peak areas (Fig. 3B).

Fig. 3: Chromatogram of GC-MS analysis of *A. multiflora*: A, Ethanol root extract; B, Aqueous root extract; C, Ethanol leaf extract; D, Aqueous leaf extract.

A

Fig. 4: A-B, Histogram and bubble graph representing number of compounds detected in *A. multiflora* leaf and root extracts.

Table 3: Phytochemical compounds detected from GC-MS analysis of the aqueous extract of *Aerides multiflora* root.

Retenti on time	Area %	Compound	CAS	Molecular weight	Molecular formula	Chemical structure
15.863	2.55	Benzene, 1,3-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-	1014-60-4	190	C ₁₄ H ₂₂	
20.343	0.74	Tetradecane	629-59-4	198	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	
21.692	0.52	Cyclohexane, octyl-	1795-15-9	196	C ₁₄ H ₂₈	
22.154	0.92	Cycloheptasiloxane, tetradecamethyl-	107-50-6	518	C ₁₄ H ₄₂ O ₇ Si ₇	
23.300	0.87	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4	206	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	
20.119	1.75	1-Tetradecanol	112-72-1	214	C ₁₄ H ₃₀ O	
25.569	0.88	Heptadecane	629-78-7	240	C ₁₇ H ₃₆	
30.089	1.81	1-Hexadecanol	36653-82-4	242	C ₁₆ H ₃₄ O	
30.233	1.27	Heneicosane	629-94-7	296	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	

32.506	0.89	7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9	82304-66-3	276	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₃	
33.566	1.03	Dibutyl phthalate	84-74-2	278	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄	
34.323	2.50	Behenic alcohol	661-19-8	326	C ₂₂ H ₄₆ O	
34.451	1.57	Tetracosane	646-31-1	338	C ₂₄ H ₅₀	
35.749	2.67	Cyclooctasiloxane, hexadecamethyl-	556-68-3	592	C ₁₆ H ₄₈ O ₈ Si ₈	
38.191	1.44	Bacteriochlorophyll-c-stearyl	0-00-0	840	C ₅₂ H ₇₂ MgN ₄ O ₄	
38.329	1.07	Cyclononasiloxane, octadecamethyl-	556-71-8	666	C ₁₈ H ₅₄ O ₉ Si ₉	
41.836	2.40	Dotriacontane	544-85-4	450	C ₃₂ H ₆₆	
42.026	0.40	Phenol, 2,2'-methylenebis[6-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-methyl-	119-47-1	340	C ₂₃ H ₃₂ O ₂	
40.719	3.11	Cyclodecasiloxane, eicosamethyl-	18772-36-6	740	C ₂₀ H ₆₀ O ₁₀ Si ₁₀	
43.506	1.43	Tetrapentacontane	5856-66-6	758	C ₅₄ H ₁₁₀	

Table 4: Phytochemical compounds detected in GC-MS analysis of the ethanol extract of *Aerides multiflora* root.

Retention time	Area %	Compound	CAS	Molecular weight	Molecular formula	Chemical structure
15.860	1.29	Benzene, 1,3-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-	1014-60-4	190	C ₁₄ H ₂₂	
20.110	0.54	1-Tetradecanol	112-72-1	214	C ₁₄ H ₃₀ O	
20.339	0.34	Tetradecane	629-59-4	198	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	
21.688	0.11	Cyclohexane, octyl-	1795-15-9	196	C ₁₄ H ₂₈	

23.296	0.48	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4	206	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	
25.373	0.61	1-Hexadecanol	36653-82-4	242	C ₁₆ H ₃₄ O	
25.557	0.43	Heptadecane	629-78-7	240	C ₁₇ H ₃₆	
31.810	0.26	10-Nonadecanone	504-57-4	282	C ₁₉ H ₃₈ O	
32.207	2.52	Lidocaine	137-58-6	234	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O	
32.502	0.23	7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9	82304-66-3	276	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₃	
33.513	1.04	Dibutyl phthalate	84-74-2	278	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄	
33.675	4.40	n-Hexadecanoic acid	57-10-3	256	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	
30.064	0.74	Behenic alcohol	661-19-8	326	C ₂₂ H ₄₆ O	
30.218	0.88	Heneicosane	629-94-7	296	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	
36.594	0.28	Phytol	150-86-7	296	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	
37.037	2.19	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-	60-33-3	280	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	
37.146	1.67	9-Tetradecenal, (Z)-	53939-27-8	210	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ O	
37.524	0.67	Linoleic acid ethyl ester	544-35-4	308	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ O ₂	
37.614	6.70	Octadecanoic acid	57-11-4	284	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	
38.172	1.05	Bacteriochlorophyll l-c-stearyl	0-00-0	840	C ₅₂ H ₇₂ Mg N ₄ O ₄	
40.013	0.75	Erucic acid	112-86-7	338	C ₂₂ H ₄₂ O ₂	
41.349	0.33	2-Methyltetracosane	1560-78-7	352	C ₂₅ H ₅₂	
45.089	2.76	Dotriacontane	544-85-4	450	C ₃₂ H ₆₆	
46.634	3.80	Tetrapentacontane	5856-66-6	758	C ₅₄ H ₁₁₀	

48.324	1.43	Squalene	111-02-4	410	C ₃₀ H ₅₀	
52.761	1.37	alpha.-Tocopherol- .beta.-D-mannoside	0-00-0	592	C ₃₅ H ₆₀ O ₇	
53.921	1.88	Ergosterol	57-87-4	396	C ₂₈ H ₄₄ O	
54.665	3.85	Stigmasterol	83-48-7	412	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ O	

Table 5: Phytochemical compounds detected in GC-MS analysis of the aqueous extract of *Aerides multiflora* leaf.

Retention time	Area %	Compound	CAS	Molecular weight	Molecular formula	Chemical structure
14.104	1.94	1-Dodecanol	112-53-8	186	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ O	
15.866	3.86	Benzene, 1,3-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-	1014-60-4	190	C ₁₄ H ₂₂	
21.681	0.41	Cyclohexane, octyl-	1795-15-9	196	C ₁₄ H ₂₈	
20.107	2.28	1-Tetradecanol	112-72-1	214	C ₁₄ H ₃₀ O	
23.289	0.54	Phenol, 3,5-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-	1138-52-9	206	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	
25.375	3.69	1-Hexadecanol	36653-82-4	242	C ₁₆ H ₃₄ O	
25.561	1.70	Hexadecane	544-76-3	226	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	
30.073	2.13	Behenic alcohol	661-19-8	326	C ₂₂ H ₄₆ O	
34.444	2.07	Heneicosane	629-94-7	296	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	
38.189	1.54	Bacteriochlorophyll-c-stearyl	0-00-0	840	C ₅₂ H ₇₂ Mg N ₄ O ₄	
38.292	2.78	Dotriacontane	544-85-4	450	C ₃₂ H ₆₆	
42.027	1.03	Phenol, 2,2'-methylenebis[6-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-methyl-	119-47-1	340	C ₂₃ H ₃₂ O ₂	
45.092	3.16	Tetracosane	646-31-1	338	C ₂₄ H ₅₀	

Table 6: Phytochemical compounds detected in GC-MS analysis of the ethanol extract of *Aerides multiflora* leaf.

Retention time	Area %	Compound	CAS	Molecular weight	Molecular formula	Chemical structure
15.850	0.89	Benzene, 1,3-bis(1,1 dimethylethyl)-	1014-60-4	190	C ₁₄ H ₂₂	
20.316	0.25	Tetradecane	629-59-4	198	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	
23.257	0.37	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4	206	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	
20.090	0.42	1-Tetradecanol	112-72-1	214	C ₁₄ H ₃₀ O	
25.346	0.67	1-Hexadecanol	36653-82-4	242	C ₁₆ H ₃₄ O	
25.536	0.42	Hexadecane	544-76-3	226	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	
29.375	0.63	Tetradecanoic acid	544-63-8	228	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	
29.880	1.89	Eicosen-1-ol, cis-9-	112248-30-3	296	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	
31.101	0.66	Phytyl stearate	62172-54-7	562	C ₃₈ H ₇₄ O ₂	
31.787	0.26	10-Nonadecanone	504-57-4	282	C ₁₉ H ₃₈ O	
32.485	0.38	7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9	82304-66-3	276	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₃	
33.497	1.15	Dibutyl phthalate	84-74-2	278	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄	
33.684	7.66	n-Hexadecanoic acid	57-10-3	256	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	
34.108	2.24	3,5-di-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid	20170-32-5	278	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₃	
30.047	1.17	Behenic alcohol	661-19-8	326	C ₂₂ H ₄₆ O	
39.887	0.90	Octacosanol	557-61-9	410	C ₂₈ H ₅₈ O	
30.201	0.79	Heneicosane	629-94-7	296	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	
36.575	3.78	Phytol	150-86-7	296	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O	
36.875	0.54	Heptadecanoic acid, 16-methyl-, methyl ester	5129-61-3	298	C ₁₉ H ₃₈ O ₂	
37.025	1.35	9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-	60-33-3	280	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	

37.137	1.49	Ethyl Oleate	111-62-6	310	C ₂₀ H ₃₈ O ₂	
37.504	0.93	Linoleic acid ethyl ester	544-35-4	308	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ O ₂	
37.602	5.77	Octadecanoic acid	57-11-4	284	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	
38.146	0.97	Octadecanoic acid, ethyl ester	111-61-5	312	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O ₂	
39.997	0.66	Erucic acid	112-86-7	338	C ₂₂ H ₄₂ O ₂	
40.079	0.73	Tetracontane	4181-95-7	562	C ₄₀ H ₈₂	
41.606	0.74	Hexanedioic acid, bis(2-ethylhexyl) ester	103-23-1	370	C ₂₂ H ₄₂ O ₄	
41.814	1.95	Dotriacontane	544-85-4	450	C ₃₂ H ₆₆	
40.708	0.60	Cyclodecasiloxane, eicosamethyl-	18772-36-6	740	C ₂₀ H ₆₀ O ₁₀ Si ₁₀	
43.376	1.70	Octacosanol	557-61-9	410	C ₂₈ H ₅₈ O	
46.614	2.03	Hexacontane	7667-80-3	842	C ₆₀ H ₁₂₂	
47.050	0.96	Tetracosamethyl-cyclododecasiloxane	18919-94-3	888	C ₂₄ H ₇₂ O ₁₂ Si ₁₂	
48.112	0.69	Tetrapentacontane	5856-66-6	758	C ₅₄ H ₁₁₀	
49.575	1.13	1-Hexacosanol	506-52-5	382	C ₂₆ H ₅₄ O	
51.462	3.26	beta.-Tocopherol	148-03-8	416	C ₂₈ H ₄₈ O ₂	
52.741	1.52	alpha.-Tocopherol-.beta.-D-mannoside	0-00-0	592	C ₃₅ H ₆₀ O ₇	

Ethanol extract of *A. multiflora* leaf was observed to contain 36 compounds of which n-Hexadecanoic acid, 3,5-di-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid, Octadecanoic acid, Behenic alcohol, Dibutyl phthalate, Phytol, beta.-Tocopherol, and Eicosen-1-ol, cis-9- are in greater concentrations (Fig. 3C). Aqueous extract of leaf showed 13 compounds; in this case Benzene, 1,3-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-, 1-Tetradecanol, 1-Hexadecano, Hexadecane, Behenic alcohol, Heneicosane, Bacteriochlorophyll-c-stearyl, Dotriacontane, Phenol, 2,2'-methylenebis[6-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-methyl-, Tetracosane were the major compounds with % peak areas more than 1% (Fig. 3D). Comparative analysis, however, revealed 7 compounds to be common between the two different solvent extracts of leaf (Fig. 4 A).

Certain compounds found in the presently studied species, such as Phytol (*Papilionanthe teres*^[35] and *Vanda cristata*^[30]), n-Hexadecanoic acid (*Dendrobium aphyllum*,^[36] *D. amoenum*,^[37] and *D. moschatum*^[38]), Hexadecane (*Dendrobium transparens*^[39]), Dibutyl phthalate, 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-, methyl ester, and Stigmasterol (*Vanda cristata*^[30]) have also been previously reported in other orchids species. Occurrence of these related phytochemicals during the present study, may authenticate their presence in the family Orchidaceae.

Interestingly, Thant et al.^[10] revealed the presence of three biphenanthrene derivatives named aerimultins A, B, C, and a new natural phenylpropanoid ester dihydrosinapyldihydroferulate, together with six other compounds Agrostonin, Imbricatin, 6- Methoxy coelonin, Gigantol, Dihydroconiferyldihydro-p-coumarate, 5-Methoxy-9,10- dihydrophenanthrene-2,3,7-triol from the MeOH extract of *A. multiflora* whole plant through solvent partition and repeated chromatography whereas our investigation in the same species, employing a different solvent, could not detect these compounds, highlighting thereby the impact of extraction methods followed for phytochemical analysis.

In the presently investigated species *A. multiflora*, majority of compounds were detected by the GC-MS analysis. GC-MS analysis has been extensively applied to various other medicinal orchids, including *Calanthe tricarinata*,^[27] *Cymbidium aloifolium*,^[40] *Dendrobium candidum*,^[41] *D. nobile*,^[42] *Rhynchostylis retusa*,^[27] *Satyrium nepalense*,^[27] *Vanda cristata*,^[30] and *V. testacea*^[43] by a few researchers, shedding light on their phytochemical composition and potential applications. The present detected compounds were found to have different biological activities. Octadecanoic acid is a stearic acid known to possess antifungal, hypocholesterolemic, antitumour, antibacterial, and hence can be used in cosmetics, as flavouring agent, and also as lubricant,^[44,45] Other presently detected compounds such as Cyclooctasiloxane, hexadecamethyl-, Cyclodecasiloxane, eicosamethyl-, 3,5-di-tert-Butyl-4-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid, Heneicosane, Heptadecanoic acid,16-methyl-, methyl ester, Hexanedioic acid, bis(2-ethylhexyl) ester have earlier been reported to possess antimicrobial activity.^[47,48,49,50] Phytol, precursor to synthetic vitamins E and K, shows sensitivity to breast cancer cell lines (MCF7), and has also been indicated to have its use as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, diuretic, antifungal, and in antimalarial activities.^[45,50] Stigmasterol is known to possess antimutagenic, Cholesterol-lowering, anti-osteoarthritic, thyroid inhibitory, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, antiosteoarthritic, antiviral, cancer-preventive and

antioxidant properties.^[51,52] Furthermore, n-Hexadecanoic acid commonly known as palmitic acid, has been reported to exhibit antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hypocholesterolemia, alpha-reductase inhibitor, selective inhibition of DNA topoisomerase-I, cancer preventive, hepatoprotective, antiandrogenic, and antiarthritic properties.^[53,54] Dotriacontane was also earlier found to possess antifungal, lubricant, and anti-corrosive properties.^[55]

As the presence of a variety of bioactive chemicals in the presently investigated species, *A. multiflora* strongly supports its use in traditional medicine to treat a range of illnesses, the identification and isolation of these compounds may be very beneficial in the formulation of novel medications.

CONCLUSION

Present phytochemical investigation revealed the presence of fifty identified phytochemicals in *Aerides multiflora* leaf and root (Aqueous and Ethanol) extracts. The abundance of flavonoids and phenols present in this plant may be responsible for its antioxidant activity. Different pharmaceutical properties of these detected compounds though have been reported, these are yet to be further examined so as to substantiate the benefit of these ingredients in pharmaceutical products. Further research on separation and isolation of pure compounds from *A. multiflora* is recommended so as to showcase its pharmacological properties via preclinical and clinical studies so that their potential may be utilized for the development of a potential novel drugs.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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